

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DIARRA****FIRST NAME: EMMANUEL****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: Not calculated

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE DMCR ACA-401D

1. EUCLID guidelines for essays indicate that the first step to writing a clear essay should be to:
 - Write short sentences, avoid page-long paragraphs, and be careful to signal transitions.¹**
 - Start with long and broad ideas and sentences and narrow them down.
 - Stay focused on the work and not spend any single day without working on the essay.
 - Draft an introduction, body, supporting sentences, evidence, and analysis.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 14.

2. EUCLID's course Pack for Period 1 indicates that to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to:
- Properly write the name of the author and the sector.
 - Properly write the book's title, the author's name, and the pages.
 - Properly write the year of the edition and the name.
 - Properly cite the author or source that has provided the information you are using.²**
3. Different organizations can recommend some specific ways of formatting documents. Everything is about style. Then the style guide is:
- The use of recommended police and font.
 - A means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent.³**
 - The use of appropriate wording.
 - The use of best ideas and information collected from excellent authors in the field.
4. According to EUCLID's course Pack for Period 1, abbreviations should be used only:
- When we don't know the full wording.
 - When the word is too long?
 - In contexts where they are clear to readers.⁴**
 - When it refers to a famous, well-known word.

² Ibid., 34.

³ Ibid., 41.

⁴ Ibid., 44.

5. According to Turabian, research is:
- A process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that not only the researcher but also others want to solve.⁵**
 - A way to prove that you are qualified to teach.
 - When we look for arguments to oppose a book.
 - A process to expose your knowledge in a domain.
6. Turabian indicates that we start a research project on a topic when:
- We already know more about the topic.
 - We want to know more about the topic than others, including a teacher or advisor.
 - We already have relevant documentation on the topic.
 - We want to know more about the topic than we do now.⁶**
7. According to Turabian, the argument is:
- More like a conversation with a community of receptive but skeptical colleagues.⁷**
 - To win, bludgeon or intimidate one's opponent into assent or silence.
 - To prove that former works on the topic are wrong.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 18.

⁶ Ibid., 24.

⁷ Ibid., 56.

8. According to Turabian, the researcher must cite the sources for the following reasons:

- Give credit, reassure readers about accuracy, show readers the research tradition that informs your work, and help readers follow or extend your research.**⁸
- To show that he/she has combined primary and secondary data.
- To prove he/she has consulted many documents on the topic.
- To build the research on existing works.

9. According to Sampson Jr., the dissertation concept paper is:

- The prospectus of the dissertation.
- A complete plan for executing the dissertation.
- A brief twelve-to-fifteen-page research proposal that describes what might be studied, why and how.**⁹
- A summary of the dissertation for busy readers.

10. The English Style Guide of the European Commission, Directorate-General for translation is intended primarily for:

- English-language authors and translators, both in-house and freelance, working for the European Commission.**¹⁰
- English language authors and translators.
- English language authors and translators working for the European Union.
- Researchers, translators, and staff working for the European Commission.

⁸ Ibid., 140.

⁹ James P. Sampson, 2017. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

¹⁰ European Union. *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (Brussels: European Union, 2021), 6.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

European Union. *English Style Guide. A handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. Brussels: European Union, 2021.

Sampson, James P. Jr. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.